

ENERGY EFFICIENCY IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SUPPLY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7572635>

Abstract: The article provides information about the benefits of obtaining electricity in the field of hydropower.

Key words: Renewable, electricity, hydropower, hydraulics, industry, resource, greenhouse

Due to the growing demand for electricity in our country, the issue of saving fuel and energy resources is becoming an extremely urgent task. In this sense, it is possible to partially solve this problem by applying and using energy-saving equipment and technologies. One of the important tasks of the energy strategy of our republic is to fully and reliably provide the population and the country's economy with energy resources, as well as to encourage energy efficiency. As a result of the analysis of the prospects for the development of lighting technologies, it was recognized as the most advanced direction to replace outdated incandescent lamps with energy-saving ones.

Incandescent lamps, which turned 125 years old in 2006 and have gained great importance in the development of mankind, are today completely obsolete light sources. In many countries of the world, in particular, in Korea, China, the USA, the European Union and the CIS countries, efforts are being made to ensure energy efficiency and manage evening peak loads, as well as introducing a system of "social tariffs" for electricity payment. fundamental measures are being taken to abandon the use of incandescent lamps.

Thus, judging by the principle of operation of incandescent lamps, their efficiency is less than 5 percent. This means that 95% of electricity is used for heating and only 5% for lighting. According to the regulations, the service life is about 1000 hours.

Energy-saving lamps last 10 times longer than incandescent lamps, and light efficiency is 4-5 times higher. If the energy efficiency indicator of lighting equipment "lumen/watt" is not less than 13 lm per 1 watt of electric power in incandescent lamps, it is 65 lumen/watt in fluorescent lamps, and 110 lumen/watt in LED lamps.

When using energy-saving lamps with the same level of illumination as incandescent lamps, electricity consumption is reduced by at least 5 times. No less than 19 percent of the total consumed electricity is used for lighting. Calculations show that 40-50 percent of the electricity consumed today can be saved by using energy-saving technologies, modern light sources and lighting systems.

There are more than 5.5 million household subscribers - electricity consumers in Uzbekistan. If 2 100 W incandescent lamps in each family are replaced by 18-22 W energy-saving lamps, the amount of 880 MW (0.08 kW x 2 units x 5,500,000 subscribers = 880,000 kW) or Talimarjon IES more power is released than the capacity of a large power plant. This will help to strengthen the stability of the republic's electricity network and provide uninterrupted electricity to all consumers.

If we consider the daily average duration of these lamps as 6 hours, the electricity economy is 158,400 thousand kWh per month (880,000 kW x 6 hours x 30 days), that is, the total daily average for the republic equal to the consumption of electricity.

In July-August of this year, the draft decision "On measures to expand the local production of energy-saving lamps" was put up for discussion on the website of the Unified Interactive Public Services Portal.

This document, together with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 86 of April 9, 2015 "On measures to introduce a system of mandatory marking and certification of energy-related household electrical appliances, newly constructed buildings and structures" on April 9, 2015, It is aimed at solving the problem of reducing electricity consumption by utility-household consumers, and ensures the solution of the problem of stable supply of electricity to the regions.

This decision envisages the gradual restriction of the use of incandescent lamps by replacing them with energy-saving ones, both in the utility sector and in various sectors of the economy. It is also planned to restrict the import, supply and sale of incandescent lamps for general use in the republican market.

Currently, there are more than 8 enterprises producing energy-saving lamps in Uzbekistan, and in 2014 they sold 6.7 mln. More than one lamp of this type was produced.

More than 6.6 million units of energy-saving lamps are produced by "Uzeltexanoat" AK, "Angren" MIZ and "Jizzakh" MIZ, of which 3.2 million. grain LED lamps. By 2021, the annual volume of production of this type of lamps at

these enterprises will be 15.7 million. exceeds the grain. In addition, restricting the sale and use of incandescent lamps creates a competitive environment for other manufacturers and creates the basis for an increase in the production of this type of lamps in our country.

The consistent application of the adopted decision in practice will ensure not only the efficient use of electricity for lighting purposes, but also the creation of new jobs at local enterprises due to the expansion of the production of energy-saving lamps.

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